

Case studies of people with diagnosed or suspected dementia in prison: Phase 2 Report

UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST of SCOTLAND
UWS

Alzheimer
Scotland Centre
for Policy and
Practice

*This work is supported by
The Dunhill Medical Trust
(Grant number RPGF/2006\236)*

Remarkable research
for healthy ageing
THE DUNHILL MEDICAL TRUST

About the study

This mixed methods study aimed to identify and develop new and effective ways to improve the health and well-being of the increasing numbers of older people living with a diagnosed or suspected dementia in prison.

Twenty semi-structured interviews were completed with staff to identify the current ways people with a suspected dementia were identified, referred, diagnosed and provided with post-diagnostic care in four prisons in Scotland with the largest number of people over 65 years (Phase 1).

The staff who participated included nurses based in prison healthcare centres, prison social workers, sessional support staff such as GPs, psychologists and forensic psychiatrists, Scottish prison service staff and staff contracted by the Scottish prison services to provide personal care.

Through interviews with a further four staff and five men living with diagnosed or suspected dementia and data from the healthcare records of the five men we gained an in-depth picture into their lived care experience (Phase 2).

This understanding informed the co-production of an evidence informed model of care and care pathway that inform and improve pre and post diagnostic care for people living with a diagnosed or suspected dementia in prison (Phase 3).

Why this study is important

Prisoners with a suspected or diagnosed dementia are becoming an increasing concern to prison services and prison healthcare staff due to the complexity of their health and social care needs. There is very little known about this population or how they are cared for in Scotland. Suggestions for how to care for this marginalised group needs to move beyond speculation if we are to develop new effective ways to improve their health and well-being.

The number of people over 60 years of age trebled in UK prisons between 2002 and 2016. Recent data from England (Forsyth et al. 2020) suggested a much higher prevalence of dementia in prisons than found among community populations of the same age.

Improved ways of recognising and managing the increasing number of older prisoners with complex health needs including dementia is urgent. The consequences of not doing so may heighten fear and distress, reduce opportunities to access appropriate healthcare interventions and support, and violate human rights.

This study offers a model of care to develop evidence informed approaches to timely identification and diagnosis that would have many benefits to people with dementia and those who support them. It offers a co-produced evidence-informed care pathway that could serve as a tool for change that would enable the right care, at the right time, by the right people, and provide an opportunity to assess risk and plan care for the future.

About the phase 2 report

This report is the second in a series of five reports. It focuses on the findings of phase 2 of the larger study described above. It presents the findings from interviews with five men living with a diagnosed or suspected dementia and four staff involved in their care and support. The men lived and the staff worked in the four prisons in Scotland that house the highest number of men over 65 years.

The interviews with the men explored what they recollected about how their cognitive issues were identified, their life in prison, how they were managing with the activities of daily living, the support they received and plans or thoughts about progression and release. The interviews with the staff, who were nominated by the men, explored what they knew about how the person was identified and assessed, their everyday life, enablers and barriers to providing care, any interventions in place to promote their well-being, issues relating to risk, progression and release, and what dementia education they had and felt they needed.

In addition, prison healthcare staff provided us with data from the men's healthcare records. The three data sources were combined to develop 5 case studies to provide an in-depth picture of living with diagnosed or suspected cognitive impairment or dementia in prison.

This report provides some concluding points from phase 2, the recommendations arising from the entire study can be found in the final report and the lay summary.

The other reports from the study can be found below:

1. Health and social care provision to people living with a diagnosed or suspected dementia living in four Scottish prisons: **Phase 1 Report**
2. Co-designed evidenced informed healthcare pathways for people living with a diagnosed or suspected dementia living in Scottish prisons: **Phase 3 Report**
3. The health and social care of people living with diagnosed or suspected dementia in prison: **Final Project Report**
4. The health and social care of people living with diagnosed or suspected dementia in prison: **Final Lay Report**

Case Study Findings

Five case studies were developed. Each case study comprised of interview data with the men who had a diagnosed or suspected dementia, the staff member they nominated, and data from the men's healthcare records. The information from the healthcare records was extracted by prison healthcare staff on to a questionnaire provided by the research team. All data was gathered during 2022. All participants were given a pseudonym to preserve anonymity.

Table 1 outlines the key case characteristics gathered from the information from the men's health care records.

The age range of the men was 60-79 years. All were on long term sentences (over four years). Only one had a clinical diagnosis of dementia. All had multiple co-morbidities, this ranged from 3-8; all were prescribed multiple medications, this ranged from 4-11. Two of the men were in receipt of personal care provided by external carers contracted by the prison service. This meant they had been assessed by the nursing team as requiring support to meet their fundamental care needs such as washing, dressing etc. Three has significant mobility issues and either used a walking frame and or wheelchair to mobilise. When asked who we could speak to get insight into their lives in prison all the men nominated staff.

Table 1: Case characteristics

Pseudonym and case study number	Age	Sentence length	Diagnosed Dementia	Number of other health conditions	Number of prescribed medications	Receives Personal care	Mobility issues	Nominated other
Davy - Case study 1	63	5 years	No	4	7	No	No	Prison officer
Kenny - Case study 2	68	12 years	No	3	4	No	No	Prison officer
Fraser - Case study 3	67	4 years	Yes	8	10	Yes	Yes	Mental Health Nurse
George- Case study 4	79	8 years	No	6	11	Yes	Yes	Mental Health Nurse
Robert - Case study 5	60	9 years	No	6	9	No	Yes	Mental Health Nurse

How a suspected dementia was identified, assessed, and health and social care needs met.

Identification, screening and assessment

Table 2 below illustrates what we know about how the five men came to the attention of the Mental Health Team (MHT), the screening, assessment and referral processes used, based on the data retrieved from the men's healthcare records. 'Not documented' indicates the information was not provided to us via the returned questionnaires.

Table 2: Identification, screening and assessment

Pseudonym and case study number	Age	Reason and person who referred to MHT	Date of referral to MHT	Length of time undergoing cognitive assessment	Cognitive screen results	Other tests	Referred to old age psychiatry	Other referrals	Status at time of data collection
Davy - Case study 1	63	Self 'pre-sentencing cognitive issues'	March 2022	2 months	Not documented	Not documented	Not documented	Sessional GP	Initiating screening and assessment
Kenny - Case study 2	68	Social work for 'cognitive issues'	August 2022	4 months	2022 MMSE 22/30 2022 MMSE 18/30	Bloods	Yes	Sessional GP	Awaiting response for old age psychiatry
Fraser - Case study 3	67	Not documented	Not documented	1 month	Cognitive screen 2020 score not documented	Not documented	Not documented	Not documented	Diagnosed dementia. No other data
George- Case study 4	79	Prison staff or 'cognitive issues'	March 2021	15 months	2021 ACE-R 68/100	CT scan x1	Yes, requested CT scan	Sessional forensic psychiatrist	Awaiting sessional psychiatrist to refer back to old age psychiatry
Robert - Case study 5	60	Prison staff for 'communication, behaviour and memory issues'	May 2018	4 years	2018 MMSE 22/30 2020 MMSE 25/30 2021 MMSE 22/30 2022 ACE-R 52/100 2022 ACE-R 51/100	CT Scan x4 Bloods x2 ECG	No	Neurology Sessional forensic psychiatrist	Awaiting referral to appropriate service

One man had self-referred to the healthcare team because he reported being increasingly concerned about memory loss that he had been experiencing prior to being sentenced. Two men had been referred to healthcare by prison staff one by a social worker. These men had been in prison for many months or years so were well known to prison staff and would have had contact with NHS staff for their medications and other health conditions. Three men hadn't approached prison or NHS staff about any cognitive issues, two couldn't recall undergoing any tests. One man had been clinically diagnosed with dementia, however we don't know how he came to the attention of healthcare staff. The screening results suggest that three men were showing signs of moderate or significant cognitive impairment. However, before a diagnosis of dementia can be given, test results need to be considered alongside a clinical history and assessment, observation of symptoms and other possible causes of cognitive impairment.

As described in the phase 1 report, it was usually the mental health nurse who carried out initial cognitive screening. If more extensive cognitive screening and assessment was required, the mental health nurses, sometimes in conjunction with the GPs, would gather more in-depth health histories and conduct further tests and involve a sessional forensic psychiatrist and or psychologist. The process of cognitive screening and the tools used across the four prisons varied; the MMSE and ACE-R¹ were those used in the cognitive assessment of the men presented in the case studies. Though the ACE-R has been updated to the ACE-III to improve the performance of the test and avoid a potential copyright violation by replacing the elements shared with the MMSE.

As described in the phase 1 report the staff took a 'case by case' approach to someone presenting with cognitive impairment as there was no formal healthcare pathway to follow. The prison healthcare staff from the case studies, like those from phase 1, felt they had insufficient knowledge and experience in dementia assessment or diagnosis processes. They felt able to, and did undertake, clinical histories, cognitive screening, blood requests and referrals for CT scans, but felt that a specialist clinician, such as an old age psychiatrist needed to be involved in the diagnostic process.

“So we'd see them, and we'd do an Addenbrooke's screening. And then discuss the findings on that, with the psychiatrist, and if we felt that they needed to be seen by psychiatry we'd get them referred to psychiatry. Well that's where it becomes quite difficult, because our psychiatrist at the moment, and they would freely admit that they don't have a great deal of knowledge on old age psychiatry. So they would then speak to one of their colleagues, and ask them what they thought and what they should do, what would be the treatment. An ideal world would be to have an older age psychiatrist designated to the prisons. Whether it be working between ourselves and [other prison] once a month. We already have somebody who's a specialist in ADHD and ASD, who's allocated to the prison. And then we'd be able to refer on to that person, who then would be able to advise us where we're to go. Because from diagnosis, it... that's where it becomes very unclear for us. Because we know what to do to get somebody into our service and be diagnosed, but afterwards we're unclear, because as I say, most of us don't have a lot of experience, particularly with dementia”.

Mental Health Nurse: Case Study 3

¹ In both cognitive tests (MMSE, ACE-R); the higher the score denotes better cognitive functioning. An ACE-R score of 51/100 indicates significant cognitive impairment, an ACE-R score of 68/100 and an MMSE score of 18 indicates moderate cognitive impairment.

It seemed that the 'case by case' approach meant there was no specific point in the assessment process that the prison healthcare teams would seek the input from community old age psychiatry teams. The old age psychiatry teams sometimes wanted the prison healthcare teams to do more tests and scans before they became involved. However, during phase 2 data collection we found that one prison had newly established a cognitive screening and assessment process in collaboration with their local health board old age psychiatry team.

“We go and see him, we do a ... what we call a triage mental health assessment. And we bring him back to the clinical team meeting for discussion. The clinical team meeting will decide what the issue is. Typically we'll do an ACE-III. And we will do a complete bloods work up, ECG, urine analysis, B- blood sugar monitoring. So we'll do a whole raft of that. Continue to see the person. Interview other people who are involved with him, to see how he presents on a day-to-day basis, to try and get a rounded corroborative picture for him. And then when we've got all the information, and we've excluded other things, we'll ask for a CT scan. That is where things start to fall down. Because CT scans, even urgent CT scans, can take up to six months. So once we've collated that information, and we have the CT scan result, then we would request an assessment by psychiatry of old age. However, we would make these requests, and they... we didn't have input until May this year [2022], when eventually we got a referral system in place, so...we can now do onward referral to a memory clinic, for instance, for further assessment, we didn't have that before. We've got the bones of it now”.

Mental Health Nurse: Case Study 4 and 5

This newly agreed referral pathway asks the prison healthcare team to undertake a comprehensive and lengthy testing and assessment process prior to them referring the old age psychiatry team.

“And they said that, if there is a concern due to a one-to-two-year history of cognitive changes, if we can provide a collateral history, an IQCODE² to assess functional level, ACE III to assess cognition, routine bloods plus thyroid, calcium, B12 and folate, and the CT [scan] referral, once they're done, and once all the results are back, then we can refer to the psychiatry of old age. They only... well, they will only see people over sixty-five. So if we've got anybody under sixty, we have nowhere to take them”.

Mental Health Nurse: Case Study 4 and 5

As the quote above suggests, prison healthcare staff don't know who to refer onto when the person was under 65 years. The age thresholds between the NHS and prison service differ. There is no universally accepted definition of old age in prisons, the Scottish Prison service commonly use the threshold of 55 years.

These lower age thresholds are based on evidence that suggests the health-related needs of prisoners are advanced by around 10 years, relative to people in the general population (House of Commons Justice Committee, 2021). Whereas the NHS and local Authorities commonly use 65 years to define old age and services for older people. The different age thresholds applied in prison and in the NHS can create a challenge when it comes to those in prison accessing specialist services. The process for referring those with a suspected cognitive impairment who were under 65 years remained unclear in all four prison healthcare teams.

² The IQCODE is a brief screening questionnaire to determine whether cognitive functioning has declined over time, it can be completed by the person or someone that supports the person. It is usually used in combination with other cognitive tests to improve detection of dementia.

Robert, who was 60 years old (case study 5), and lived in mainstream accommodation in the prison, had a fluctuating presentation. The nurse reported some days he was very confused, disorientated and repeatedly asking the same questions or telling the staff the same things over and over. Other days he seemed less confused and responded well to reorientation. Since 2018 the prison staff had referred Robert to healthcare several times for 'communication, behaviour and memory issues', they reported he could be irritable, hostile and aggressive.

“It's a bit more complicated than... than it at first seems. I've discussed them [Robert] with the consultant, and the consultant felt that there were underlying physical health issues that needed further investigation. Because he didn't feel that the man's cognition functioning was... after getting the results of the CT scan and the hepatology ultrasound, he didn't think that it was consistent with a presentation of any kind of dementia. He felt it was consistent with a previous subdural haematoma, and he felt that the primary care team should further investigate that. However, it doesn't matter what the label is, or what the diagnosis is, he still has impaired cognition functioning that we need to support him with”.

Mental Health Nurse: Case Study 4 and 5

Robert (case study 5) also described his fluctuating presentation; though he thought he had performed well in the cognitive tests.

“Some days I'm alright and then the odd day I'm just puzzled, you know? It's – nothing – nothing bothers me, know what I mean? That's what it's like. I've got no worries. Just sit and watch the telly, know what I mean? But it's – I'm content with that, happy at that”.

Robert: Case Study 5

Complex health and social care needs

As found in previous research, all the men had high rates of chronic health conditions (Hayes et al., 2012). Davy (case study 1) expressed less concern about his physical health than the other four men. Although he was on several medications, he was able to participate regularly in leisure and recreation activities.

The three men with mobility issues were particularly concerned about how their multiple health conditions were impacting on their quality of life. For example, Robert (case study 5) who used a walking frame, was concerned about the pain from his chronic leg ulcers which seeped and smelled and required dressing three times a week. He was also concerned about his deteriorating balance, after recently falling a few times going to the toilet at night, his worsening eyesight and not having glasses to wear due to them being broken.

George (case study 4) who was in a wheelchair and had an indwelling catheter, was also concerned about his leg ulcers not healing but was more concerned about his impaired vision and hearing. He described poor blurred vision and struggled to hear during the interview. He reported he was waiting to see the optician and his hearing aid had been in for repair for many months. Fraser (case study 3) who used a walking frame, was concerned about falling more frequently, and his worsening eyesight, he was waiting to be seen about his cataracts.

“I fall about, because I'm... I've no balance, and I keep telling them, I keep telling them and saying, “Look, I've no balance at all,” ken? “Oh right, right (name of person).” But nothing gets done. Honestly, and it's so irritating. It's difficult for me to move about myself, you know? That's terrible. I'm using that, this walker here, mainly. Well I'm... well it's quite difficult, especially in the cell because there's obstacles, you know? And you have to hang onto the sinks and hang onto the back of chairs and everything. I mean, I'm just... I'm no' doing well in my cell”.

Fraser: Case Study 3

Fraser also felt the nurses, officers and social workers deliberately withheld help and information. He was suspicious about people's motives and believed other prisoners were trying to steal his money. Staff were aware of the concerns he has raised about information being withheld and money being stolen, and he had been referred to and seen by an advocacy worker.

Four of the men exemplified how older prisoners have been described in previous reports such as 'old and quiet' (HMIPs 2004, 2022, Ridley 2022). They couldn't participate in work programmes and needed assistance if they wanted to go outside or visit the library. They largely stayed in their cell or the immediate area, relied on their cellmates or one or two other prisoners to remind them or help them with ordering, cleaning their cell, or occasionally going outside for exercise.

To try and better meet health and social care needs the prisons involved in this study tended to accommodate older men and those with health and social care needs together as much as possible. They also tried to allocate prison officers who were more experienced and or interested in working with this population to those areas. Kenny (case study 2), Fraser (case study 3) and George (case study 4) were all accommodated in areas for older prisoners, many of whom had high levels of health and care needs. The nurse who managed the care of both George (case study 4) and Robert (Case study 5) explained some of the differences between accommodation for men with high health and care needs and mainstream accommodation.

“One is getting good quality of care, or... well, better quality of care. Almost as good as you would get, I would think. Because the staff are now experienced in working with these guys, so we've had that... that sort of palliative care and high healthcare needs in for a good wee while now”.

Mental Health Nurse: Case Study 4 and 5

“The younger man is housed in mainstream conditions. His personal officer is very good. One of the other girls, she's also very good – but when they're not there, and they're getting different people on because of staffing issues, it's very, it's a different experience for him. And because his presentation fluctuates... so I saw him yesterday, and we had a really good session yesterday, compared to how I have found him in the past. But staff will report that he can be hostile and aggressive, non-compliant with his leg ulcer treatment, taking his dressings off and interfering with them. He's on Entonox, so he plays about with the Entonox and won't take it as he's supposed to take it. And then they'll have a spell of that, where he's angry and irritable all the time, and interfering and doing this... and then we'll see the man I saw yesterday, who was confused and reported things over and over again, and couldn't remember things. So he might remember this, but couldn't remember that, and repeated himself. But was pleasant, joking and laughing, and was responding well to sort of orientation and re-guidance redirection. And that is difficult stuff to grasp. “Is he at it? He's at it.” You can understand why...that fluctuating presenting, fluctuating capacity.”

Mental Health Nurse: Case Study 4 and 5

Two men, Fraser (case study 3) and George (case study 4), were in receipt of personal care. Social care is provided by external carers contracted by the Scottish Prison Service. A recent report by the Scottish Government into the social care needs of people in prison stated that social care should include support with activities of daily living, maintaining independence, managing personal relationships, taking part in prison life, and social interaction (Scottish Government 2021). Our phase 1 and 2 findings suggest that the role of external carers focussed on personal care needs as identified by the nurses: showering, using the toilet, getting dressed, eating, and drinking.

“I have carers helping me, yeah. But not with my memory, like. But the carers do help me, aye, aye. Well they help us like if I'm having an accident, like, you know? I don't like that much, like, them helping us in the shower. Because it's embarrassing. Know what I mean, that is really”.

Fraser: Case Study 3

It tended to be other prisoners who supported the men with other aspects of social care.

“They [other prisoners] get me – they get me my meals. And – and they help remind me things that I've got to do, sort of thing. I manage [eating] because they give me a table and bring it over and put it next to you”.

George: Case Study 4

There are a small number of accessible cells in prison; these tend to be slightly larger cells with a toilet. As reported in the phase 1 there were more men in need of these than there were available. Common adaptations included hospital bed and grab rails. Both Fraser (case study 3) and George (case study 4) were in accessible cells, George also had an airbed.

“As I say, we're not a twenty-four-hour support system, and I know we do have carers. But they don't just care for one person, when they come in, it's a package of care, so they have, I think there's fourteen, fifteen people at this point in time that they also have to care for. Not all on the one wing, or the same house block, they maybe have to go elsewhere, and divide their time. And I know the prison's been really good in trying to almost cohort people that need the most needs, but it's not the best environment. The cells certainly are not adapted to anybody's needs, whether somebody has dementia, or they have physical disabilities. They're not great, and it's almost like we have to prioritise who gets what cell, based on who's got the most need. Which is quite difficult, because you're having to choose who's needs are more than anybody else. So more adapted cells”.

Mental Health Nurse: Case Study 3

The health care staff felt that the aspect of care they managed best was physical health. They could request the prison service to contract external carers to provide personal care and they had primary care nurses on site

“Well that's easier for us to do, because we work in close conjunction with primary care. So for physical health, I think we're probably better at that than any other thing. We, in our mental health team, we have seven nurses. That is it. That's for nine hundred prisoners. So you can imagine certainly somebody and at the level that some of these gentleman are at, they would benefit from a lot of support, which of all the good intentions in the world, we can't offer that”.

Mental Health Nurse: Case Study 3

Based on the data from the returned questionnaires it appeared that none of the five men had required a referral or been referred to Occupational Therapy (OT), Speech and Language or Physiotherapy. Although there were mental health OTs in one healthcare team, they were contracted to see people under 65 years. Another team had been trying to recruit a physiotherapist for many months without success. The healthcare staff, like the staff in phase 1, wanted more specialist community input, specifically from mental health Occupational Therapists and Old age psychiatry teams. The NHS staff described how COVID19 had resulted in many of the sessional services, such as audiology being stopped or reduced, and that by Spring 2022 these services had begun to start up again. Also, during the intervening two years, the wait times for community services had increased. They, like the staff in phase 1, described how the setting, i.e., working within a prison, made communication, and getting a person's individual needs met more time consuming and complex.

“But again, it is – because of the limitations of the environment... so something that would be quite simple somewhere else, for instance arranging an appropriate diet... so the kitchen will take instruction from the nutritionist, who doesn't come into the prison, who will only give advice, but doesn't come in to assess people, and is reliant on our assessment. So there are assessments that we can do, but she will ask for a MUST³, which we are not all familiar with. And then the kitchen can respond with a modified diet. We do have a speech and language therapist who can assess swallowing and things like that. But it takes a prolonged period of time, and we have anticipatory care plans in place. But again, it's the way that these are communicated. And having a cohesive plan that involves all the team, and all the team that can contribute to, to support the person.”

Mental Health Nurse: Case Study 4 and 5

All prison healthcare teams held multidisciplinary healthcare team (MDT) meetings. At the time of reporting two out of three prison also had monthly interagency health care meetings to discuss and review 'people of concern' that prison staff with a management or leadership role, e.g., unit managers, Deputy Governors/Governors would attend.

“We have a healthcare meeting once a month. So anybody that has... that they're concerned about... for example, the gentleman you met today, and the other gentleman we've discussed are all part of that meeting. So anybody that we feel needs additional, so the officers will sit on that, occupational therapy will sit on that, prison psychology will sit in on that. Ourselves as well, will sit on that. And we all discuss... obviously they've given us permission to discuss their care, and what we can do to help and assist.”

Mental Health Nurse: Case Study 3

One healthcare team had been trying for several years to set up a regular multi-agency multidisciplinary health meeting that included the prison service to discuss those with high health and care needs. Although healthcare team met regularly, the current method of communication with prison staff about healthcare matters was ad-hoc meetings between healthcare staff and unit managers.

The men in case study 1 and 2 nominated prison officers to provide insights into their lives. Neither prison officer was aware that the men were undergoing cognitive assessments. Although both these men were in prisons that had monthly multiagency healthcare meetings that included prison staff, both had been under assessment for less than two months. Unless these men were 'of concern' to the NHS and or prison staff, it is unlikely that they would have been discussed at the meeting.

³ MUST³ is a five-step screening tool to identify adults who are malnourished, at risk of malnutrition (undernutrition), or obese. It also includes management guidelines which can be used to develop a care plan. It is for use in hospitals, community and other care settings and can be used by all care workers.

Prison staff would only know about people's health conditions if the person told them, the person had a communicable disease or health care staff had sought and gained consent to share healthcare information from the person. The issue of gaining consent to share was discussed.

“I've not been informed of any of the testing that's been going on for [prisoners name]. We do get informed if... like one of my prisoners has just got diagnosed with diabetes. So I got informed about that, because obviously we then need to, we now need to watch what, like, he eats, that kind of thing. Obviously with dementia, it's more just watching him as a person and watch if he does change, or something's a bit out of character. And I've not had any experience with anybody with dementia. So even just giving me a, like a heads-up, or a care plan, you know? Something such as know what to look out for”

Prison Officer: Case Study 1

Leaving prison

None of the men in the case studies were due for imminent liberation. Only one man talked about what they would do once they were release.

“But now it's gone back the way and now when I go out I need to go into a care home. When I consider all the help I get in here, you know, I need that outside”.

George: Case Study 5

The staff echoed the findings from phase 1, that they put in referrals, wrote discharge letters but arranging continuity of care was beset with complications, in part because a person's health and social care needs, capacity and risk to the public all needed to be assessed. Assessing the risk to the public of a person with dementia in these circumstances was fraught with difficulty and complexity. They reported that finding and securing alternative accommodation for people living with advanced dementia who lacked capacity, in receipt of personal care, with a criminal conviction (even if spent) was a long and challenging process as few alternatives were available. Staff reported that compassionate release was being explored for one man.

“A lot of our gentlemen that we've got in, that they're not in for a matter of months, they're in for a long time. And at the latter part of their life, they may never be liberated, which is, you know... we have our first compassionate liberation that we're looking at, due to dementia.”

Mental Health Nurse: Case Study 3

Dementia education

As found in phase 1, the dementia education staff had received varied within and between staff groups. None of the staff from phase 2 had received any dementia education in their current role.

The prison officers reported having had no dementia education during or since their training. The nursing staff reported having had some dementia education in their first professional training. Both the mental health nurses had post qualification experience of working with older people and or people living with a dementia. However, neither of them felt they had expertise in working with older people or people living with a dementia. They all felt dementia education for all NHS, prison and external care staff would be useful.

“Any training that we could get about dementia. Because it is an emerging issue. With age, find that people are being admitted into prison, it's increasing. So it's not something that's suddenly going to go away, we're going to get more and more gentlemen, and perhaps ladies as well coming in that are going to need some assistance from us. So anything, really, from the basics right up to more complex and... because we don't, unless somebody's come from a background where they've worked with dementia, then most of us are lacking within that. Because within here, we would consider that's an expertise. Like I say, we have somebody, nurses that specialise in ADHD and ASD. So we consider dementia at this point in time as a speciality as well. So it's not something that we would expect to find in a prison setting. In fact if we asked anybody coming for an interview, well we do now, and we do expect them to say that one of our emerging problems is going to be the elderly population. But it's something that has not been recognised, or indeed, yeah, I suppose when people are factoring in funding and what staffing we need for it, it's something that nobody's considered at this point.”

Mental Health Nurse: Case Study 3

“I think even giving staff more training in what to look out for, because you can obviously get the prisoners that are quite forgetful, et cetera, but just making even officers and personal officers aware that prisoners are going through testing for it. You know, because we need to know these things if we are... it's our duty of care to look after them, you know, so we need to be able to look out, and be advised that there is testing going on, so that if something was to change with them, whether it's like, “That's a bit weird,” you know, we know that there's a reason for that.”

Prison Officer: Case Study 1

Summary of findings

The age range of the men was 60-79 years, four were over 65 years. All were on long term sentences (over four years). All had multiple co-morbidities, this ranged from 3-8, all were prescribed multiple medications, this ranged from 4-11. Two of the men were in receipt of personal care provided by external carers contracted by the prison service. This meant they had been assessed by the nursing team as requiring support to meet their fundamental care needs such as washing, dressing etc. Three has significant mobility issues and either used a walking frame and or wheelchair to mobilise. Two were accommodated in accessible cells and one had an airbed. When asked who we could speak to get insight into their lives in prison all the men nominated staff. The prison officers were not aware that the two men who nominated them were undergoing assessment for cognitive impairment or dementia.

Four of the five men exemplified how older prisoners have been described previously. They couldn't participate in work programmes, needed assistance if they wanted to go outside or visit the library. They largely stayed in their cell or the immediate area, relied on their cellmates or one or two other prisoners to remind them or help them with ordering, cleaning their cell, or occasionally going outside for exercise. In interviews four out of the five men expressed that their greatest concern was around their deteriorating physical health and two about maintaining contact with family members.

Prison staff had alerted the healthcare team to two of the men, social work had alerted the healthcare team to one, one man had self-referred, and it is unknown how the other man was identified. Four of the five men were undergoing assessment for suspected dementia, the duration of the assessment period at the time of interview varied from one month to four years. The most common documented cognitive tests used were the MMSE and the ACE-R. Only one man had a confirmed clinical diagnosis of dementia.

As with phase 1, staff reported that assessing a person for dementia was often complex due to several intersecting issues related to the poor health of prison population as described above, a lack of clarity around the processes of referral and assessment and the nature of providing healthcare in a prison setting. A 'case by case' approach guided the referral and assessment process and staff roles within it. For this population prison healthcare teams felt they needed specialist input from a community old age psychiatry team. The point in the assessment process that the teams referred to old age psychiatry varied. One reported a newly established assessment and referral pathway had been agreed with their local old age psychiatry team. As found in phase 1, both prison healthcare staff didn't know or have a process for referring those with a suspected cognitive impairment who were under 65 years.

The staff reported that COVID19 restrictions had impacted on the availability of sessional support staff and referral times to community services. They also reported that getting supports such as modified diet, mobility aids etc. in place could take a long time due to a combination of getting access to some supports and complexity of organising supports within a prison regime. All the prison healthcare teams operated monthly multidisciplinary healthcare team meetings. Two of the prisons operated monthly interagency healthcare meetings that involved prison staff for people 'of concern'. In the other prison this kind of meeting was not happening, this was reported as being due to a lack of buy in from the current senior prison management. All the staff felt this kind of meeting supported communication and interagency working.

None of the men were due to be released in the next few months though all the staff anticipated finding suitable accommodation for them would be a long and complex process. One man felt he would need to be placed in a care home bed on release. All the staff felt that dementia education would support them to provide care for the increasing number of older people with cognitive impairment in prison.

Merits and limitations

To the best of our knowledge this is first study in Scotland to explore the lived experience and gather the health histories of people living with a diagnosed or suspected dementia in Scotland.

Although the prison officers felt they didn't know the men that well and one of the returned questionnaires contained scant detail about one man's health history, the approach nonetheless provides evidence critical to understanding experience of life and care for those with a diagnosed or suspected dementia in prison. It provides a robust evidence base to inform ways to support staff and improve care for this population..

Concluding points

1. Consent to share should be sought early to streamline the sharing of information within and between prison, NHS and partner agencies.
2. Education about ageing and dementia should be mandatory. All staff should be encouraged to use the dementia education resources in the NHS for Education Promoting Excellence Dementia Knowledge and Skills framework appropriate to their role.
3. Consideration should be given to implementing a care pathway that guides the processes of screening, referral, assessment and post diagnostic care.
4. Each prison should consider having a locally negotiated pathway for accessing an old age psychiatry and other appropriate specialist services for those under and over 65 years with a suspected dementia.
5. Those diagnosed with dementia should be given a formal assessment of their needs by a health or social care professional with the appropriate knowledge, skills and expertise in dementia.
6. An integrated person-centred package of care inclusive of the person and their family should be developed for these individuals to meet their biopsychosocial-spiritual needs within the prison setting.
7. Those diagnosed with dementia should have a named point of contact, professional or case manager who is a health or social care professional with the appropriate knowledge, skills and expertise in dementia.
8. People with diagnosed or suspected dementia should have access social and recreational activities tailored to their physical and mental health to promote wellbeing.
9. All prisons should consider implementing a monthly interagency healthcare meeting where these individuals are discussed and reviewed.
10. If advanced dementia care needs cannot be met within the prison setting, early consideration should be given to providing these in a more appropriate location.

References

Forsyth K, Heathcote L, Senior J et al., Dementia and mild MCI in prisoners aged over 50 years in England and Wales: a mixed-methods study. Health Services and Delivery Research, Vol 8, Issue 27. 2020 ISSN 2050-4349

Hayes, A.J., Burns, A., Turnbull, P. and Shaw, J.J., 2012. The health and social needs of older male prisoners. International journal of geriatric psychiatry, 27(11), pp.1155-1162.

Her Majesty's Inspectorate of Prisons (2004). 'No problems – old and quiet': Older prisoners in England and Wales. A thematic review by HM Chief Inspector of Prisons. London.

His Majesty's Chief Inspector of Prisons for Scotland (HMIPS) (2022) - Who Cares - A follow-up review of the lived experience of older prisoners in Scotland's prisons. <https://www.prisoninspectorscotland.gov.uk/publications/hmips-who-cares-follow-review-lived-experience-older-prisoners-scotlands-prisons>

Ridley, L. (2022). No Place for Old Men? Meeting the Needs of an Ageing Male Prison Population in England and Wales. Social Policy and Society, 21(4), 597-611. doi:10.1017/S1474746421000178

Scottish Government (2021) Prison population: social care needs. <https://www.gov.scot/publications/understanding-social-care-support-needs-scotlands-prison-population/pages/2/>

SIGN 168 (2023) [Assessment, diagnosis, care and support for people with dementia and their carers \(sign.ac.uk\)](https://www.sign.ac.uk/sign-168-assessment-diagnosis-care-and-support-for-people-with-dementia-and-their-carers)

World Health Organisation (2023) Dementia. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/dementia> [accessed 20/09/2023]

Acknowledgements

Many thanks to all the organisations and individuals who enabled this research or participated in the study sharing their experiences and views.

This project was funded by the Dunhill Medical Trust [grant number RPGF/2006\236] and focussed on improving dementia care in prisons through co-designing an evidence informed dementia care pathway and other practical resources for staff working in Scottish prisons. The study commenced in Spring 2021 and reported in early 2024.

Remarkable research
for healthy ageing
THE DUNHILL MEDICAL TRUST

About the Research Team

Dr Rhoda MacRae,
Principal Investigator and
Reader, Alzheimer Centre
for Policy and Practice,
School of Health and Life
Sciences, University of the
West of Scotland

Prof Debbie Tolson,

Co-investigator and Director, Alzheimer Centre for
Policy and Practice, School of Health and Life Sciences,
University of the West of Scotland

Dr James Taylor,

Co-investigator and Head of Division of Health and
Life Sciences, University of the West of Scotland

Dr Kirstin Anderson,

Co-investigator and Lecturer in Criminology,
Edinburgh Napier University

Dr Natalie Chalmers,

Research Associate,
University of Edinburgh

Dr Tom Russ,

External Consultant and Director, Alzheimer Scotland
Dementia Research Centre, University of Edinburgh

Prof Lindsay Thompson, External Consultant and
Medical Director of The State Hospital, University
of Edinburgh

Glossary

Cognitive or Mild cognitive impairment, often known as MCI, describes a set of symptoms, that produce a decline in mental abilities. The difficulties caused by MCI are worse than would normally be expected for a healthy person of the same age. A person with MCI has mild problems with one or more of the following: memory, reasoning, planning or problem-solving, attention, language and visual depth perception. It is estimated that between 5 and 20% of people aged over 65 have MCI. It is not a type of dementia, but a person with MCI is more likely to go on to develop dementia (Alzheimer's Society, 2023).

Dementia is an umbrella term describing a progressive neurodegenerative syndrome caused by illnesses such as Alzheimer's disease that cause structural and chemical changes to the brain. The changes most notably affect memory, orientation, comprehension, calculation, learning capacity, language, and judgement. Consciousness is not affected. The impairment in cognitive function is commonly accompanied, and occasionally preceded, by deterioration in emotional control, social behaviour, or motivation (WHO 2017). As the illness progresses the trajectory is not fixed nor predictable, and people can and do live for months and years with advanced dementia-specific palliative care needs (Reisberg et al 2006) before they reach the stage of dying with dementia.

Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA) is a short cognitive screening tool.

Mini Mental State Examination (MMSE) is a short cognitive screening tool.

6-item cognitive impairment test (6CIT) is a short cognitive screening tool.

Addenbrooke's Cognitive Examination, third revision (ACE)- III, is a more comprehensive cognitive screening tool.

Residential area is the term this report uses for describing the areas in the prison where people in prison were accommodated. The prisons had different names for these areas including hall, wing, unit, flat.

dementiainprisons.com

**Alzheimer
Scotland Centre
for Policy and
Practice**

If referring to or using material from this publication please use the following citation
MacRae, R, Tolson, D, Taylor, J, Anderson, K, Chalmers, N, Russ, R and Thompson, L (2024).
The health and social care of people with a diagnosed or suspected dementia living in
prison: Phase 2 report

